

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 108

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 108

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 108:0 A Song, a Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 108:1 שִׁיר מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : 2 נִבּוֹן</p>
<p>Psa. 108:1 "My heart is steadfast, O God;</p>	<p>לִבִּי אֱלֹהִים אֲשִׁירָה וְאֶזְמְרָה אֶת־כְּבוֹדִי : 3 עֹרָה הַנֶּבֶל וְכִנּוֹר</p>
<p>I will sing, I will sing praises, even with my ¹soul.</p>	<p>אֲעִירָה שָׁתֵר : 4 אוֹדָה בְּעַמִּים </p>
<p>² Awake, harp and lyre; I will awaken the dawn!</p>	<p>יְהוָה וְאֶזְמְרָה בְּלֹא־אֲמִים : 5 כִּי־גִדּוֹל מִעַל־שָׁמַיִם תְּסַבֵּךְ וְעַד־</p>
<p>³ I will give thanks to You, O LORD, among the peoples, And I will sing praises to You among the nations.</p>	<p>שָׁתְקִים אֲמַתְךָ : 6 רוּמָה עַל־שָׁמַיִם אֱלֹהִים וְעַל כָּל־הָאָרֶץ כְּבוֹדָךְ : 7 לְמַעַן יִחַלְצֵנִי יְדִידֶיךָ הוֹשִׁיעָה</p>
<p>⁴ For Your ^alovingkindness is great ^babove the heavens, And Your truth <i>reaches</i> to the skies.</p>	<p>יְמִינֶךָ וְעַגְנִי : 8 אֱלֹהִים וְדַבֵּר בְּקִרְשׁוֹ אֶעֱלֶזָה אֶתְחַלֵּקָה שְׁכָם וְעַמֶּק סְכוֹת אֲמַדָּד : 9 לִי גִלְעָד </p>
<p>⁵ "Be exalted, O God, above the heavens, And Your glory above all the earth.</p>	<p>לִי מְנַשֶּׁה וְאַפְרַיִם מְעוֹז רֹאשִׁי יְהוּדָה מְחַקְקִי : 10 מוֹאָב וְסִיר רַחֲצִי עַל־אֲדוֹם אֲשַׁלֵּךְ נַעְלִי עָלַי־כְּלִשֶׁת אֶתְרוּעֶע : 11 מִי זִבְלֵנִי עִיר מְבַצֵּר מִי נִתְּנִי עַד־אֲדוֹם : 12 הֲלֹא־אֱלֹהִים זָנַחְתֵּנוּ וְלֹא־תִצָּא אֱלֹהִים בְּצַבָּאֵתֵינוּ : 13 הֲבָה־לָנוּ עֲזָרַת מְצַר וְשׂוֹא תִשׁוּעַת אֲרָם : 14 בְּאֱלֹהִים נַעֲשֶׂה־חֵיל וְהוּא יְבוּס צָרֵינוּ :</p>
<p>⁶ "That Your beloved may be delivered, Save with Your right hand, and answer me!</p>	
<p>Psa. 108:7 God has spoken in His ¹holiness: "I will exult, I will portion out Shechem And measure out the valley of Succoth. ⁸ "Gilead is Mine, Manasseh is Mine; Ephraim also is the ¹helmet of My head; "Judah is My ²scepter. ⁹ "Moab is My washbowl; Over Edom I shall throw My shoe;</p>	

Over Philistia I will shout aloud.”

Psa. 108:10 “Who will bring me
into the besieged city?

Who ¹will lead me to Edom?

¹¹ Have not You Yourself, O God,
^arejected us?

And will You not go forth with our
armies, O God?

¹² Oh give us help against the
adversary,

For ^adeliverance ¹by man is in vain.

¹³ ¹Through God we will do valiantly,

And ^ait is He who shall tread down
our adversaries.

References

Psalm 108:1

¹Lit *glory*

^aPs 57:7-11; 108:1-5

Psalm 108:4

^aNum 14:18; Deut 7:9; Ps 36:5; 100:5; Mic 7:18-20

^bPs 113:4

Psalm 108:5

^aPs 57:5

Psalm 108:6

^aPs 60:5-12; 108:6-13

Psalm 108:7

¹Or *sanctuary*

Psalm 108:8

¹Lit *protection*

²Or *lawgiver*

^aGen 49:10

Psalm 108:10

¹Or *has led*

^aPs 60:9

Psalm 108:11

^aPs 44:9

Psalm 108:12

¹Lit *of*

^aIs 30:3

Psalm 108:13

¹Or *In* or *With*

^aIs 60:12; 63:1-4

Targum

Psa. 108:1 A song and Psalm composed by David. ² My heart is firm, O God; I will praise and sing indeed, my glory. ³ Sing praise, O harp and lyre; I will sing praise at dawn. ⁴ I will give thanks in your presence among the peoples, O LORD, and I will sing praise to you among the nations. ⁵ For your goodness is great above the heavens, and your truth reaches to the sky. ⁶ Be exalted above the heavens, O God, and may your glory be on all the inhabitants of the earth. ⁷ So that your beloved ones will be delivered; redeem with your right hand and answer me. ⁸ God speaks from the place of his presence ; I will be glad, I will divide spoil with the inhabitants of Shechem; and with the inhabitants of the plain of Succoth I will measure the border. ⁹ Mine is Gilead, mine is Manasseh; those of the house of Ephraim are the strength of my head, and my scribe is from those of the house of Judah. ¹⁰ I have trampled the Moabites like my washing-pot; I will cast my sandal over the kingdom of Edom; I will shout over the kingdom of the Philistines. ¹¹ And now because I sinned, who will lead me to the fortress of wicked Rome? Who led me to Constantinople of Edom? ¹² Behold, because we have sinned in the presence of the LORD he has forsaken us, and his presence does not go out with our armies. ¹³ Give us help from the oppressor, for vain is the redemption of the son of man. ¹⁴ In God we shall show might, and he will trample our oppressors.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is an almost exact duplication of Psalms 57 and 60. The Psalm says that the Messiah will deliver the people from Exile, and she will triumph over all of her enemies.

Notes on the Psalm

Refer to the notes in Psalms 57 and 60.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

